

Synthesis of Furopyrimidines : Condensation of Alkyl/Aryl Isothiocyanates with 2-Amino-3-cyanofuran Derivatives

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Condensation of a few 2-amino-3-cyano-4,5-disubstituted-furan with isothiocyanates in the presence of a base has been found to result in the formation of 3-alkyl/aryl-4-imino-5,6-disubstituted-furo[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine-2-thiones (3a-n). These compounds on refluxing with aqueous dimethylformamide was found to rearrange and form 4-arylamino-furo[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine-2-thiones.

THE furopyrimidine ring system has received much attention¹ due to their pharmacological applications¹. In an earlier study, the reaction of 2-amino-3-cyanothiophene derivatives with isothiocyanates in the presence of alkali resulted in the synthesis of thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine derivatives². This approach was extended to the synthesis of furopyrimidine derivatives. We now report the results of our investigation on the reaction of 2-amino-3-cyano-4,5-diphenylfuran and 2-amino-3-cyano-4,5-dimethylfuran with isothiocyanates. The reaction of the furan (1) and phenyl isothiocyanate did not occur even after prolonged heating in toluene. Recent experiments have revealed that amino groups having low nucleophilicity, as in thioureas, could be made to react with isothiocyanates when the reaction was conducted in polar solvents such as dimethyl formamide in the presence of powdered alkali metal hydroxides³. Therefore it was decided to employ the above reaction condition for the condensation of 1a and 1b with isothiocyanates.

2-Amino-3-cyanofuran (1a) was reacted with phenyl isothiocyanate in dimethyl formamide at room temperature in the presence of an equivalent amount of sodium hydroxide (Scheme 1) and a single

product was isolated having molecular formula $C_{24}H_{17}N_3OS$. The compound did not undergo dehydrosulphurisation test thereby showing the absence of $-NH-C(S)-NH-$ grouping in the compound⁴. The compound was soluble in 0.5 *N* aqueous sodium hydroxide and formed a monomethyl derivative on treatment with methyl iodide thus indicating the presence of an enolisable thione group in its structure. In its ir spectrum, the peak due to the cyano group at 2200 cm^{-1} , present the starting material, was absent. This indicated that rapid cyclisation of the intermediate thiourea derivative (2) had occurred in the presence of sodium hydroxide.

As a representative case the spectral data of 3-*p*-chlorophenyl-6,7-diphenyl-4-iminofuro[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine-2-thione (3c) has been discussed below. The ir spectrum showed sharp peaks at 3400 (NH) and $1640\text{ cm}^{-1}\text{ (C=N)}$ ⁵. The ¹H nmr spectrum showed a broad singlet at $\delta\ 2.3-2.5\text{ (1H)}$ due to $=NH$, another singlet at $\delta\ 5.9-6.1\text{ (1H)}$ due to NH and a multiplet at $\delta\ 7.1-7.7\text{ (14H)}$ due to two phenyl and one *p*-chlorophenyl groups. Mass spectrum of the compound showed the molecular ion peak at $m/z\ 429$ and 431 (in the intensity ratio 3:1). The presence of a peak at $m/z\ 169$ in moderate intensity, is attributed to a fragment of structure $ClC_6H_4NCS^+$ which could arise from the structure 3c (Scheme 1). The characterisation data of 3a-n and 4a-i are given in Table 1.

3-Alkyl/aryl-4-imino-5,6-diphenylfuro[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine-2-thiones were found to undergo Dimroth⁶ type rearrangement on refluxing in aqueous dimethyl formamide and yield 4-arylamino-3-alkyl/arylfuro[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine-2-thione (5a-m) (Scheme 2). Aqueous dimethyl formamide was chosen because it provides a suitable medium having good solubility and allows a high reaction temperature. Generally, in Dimroth rearrangement a basic catalyst is implied which has been suggested⁷ to be the 4-imino compound itself. Thus, it was reported that 3-phenyl-4-imino-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinazoline-2-thione on refluxing in

Scheme 1

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	R ¹ =R ²	R ³	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	ν_{\max} cm ⁻¹
3a	C ₆ H ₅	Phenyl	217	74	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ OS	3 450 (NH), 3 200 (NH), 2 990 (C-H), 1 620 (C=N), 1 240 (C=S)
3b ^a	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	210	73	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₂ OS	3 350 (NH), 3 200 (NH), 2 900 (C-H), 1 620 (C=N), 1 240 (C=S)
3c ^b	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	205	74	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ OS	3 450 (NH), 3 200 (NH), 2 990 (C-H), 1 620 (C=N), 1 240 (C=S)
3d ^c	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	218	77	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	3 350 (NH), 3 200 (NH), 2 990 (C-H), 1 620 (C=N), 1 240 (C=S)
3e ^d	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	207	70	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	3 360 (NH), 3 200 (NH), 2 990 (C-H), 1 620 (C=N), 1 240 (C=S)
3f	C ₆ H ₅	Methyl	244	68	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₂ OS	3 350 (NH), 3 200 (NH), 2 990 (C-H), 1 620 (C=N), 1 240 (C=S)
3g	C ₆ H ₅	<i>n</i> -Propyl	210	50	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₂ OS	3 350 (NH), 3 200 (NH), 2 990 (C-H), 1 620 (C=N), 1 240 (C=S)
3h	C ₆ H ₅	Isopropyl	205	62	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₂ OS	3 350 (NH), 3 200 (NH), 2 990 (C-H), 1 620 (C=N), 1 240 (C=S)
3i	C ₆ H ₅	<i>n</i> -Butyl	212	50	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₂ OS	3 350 (NH), 3 200 (NH), 2 990 (C-H), 1 650 (C=N), 1 240 (C=S)
3j ^e	CH ₃	Phenyl	208	55	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ OS	3 430 (NH), 3 200 (NH), 2 990 (C-H), 1 620 (C=N), 1 170 (C=S)
3k	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	247	63	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₂ OS	3 460 (NH), 3 200 (NH), 2 990 (C-H), 1 620 (C=N), 1 170 (C=S)
3l	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	210	68	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ ClN ₂ OS	3 430 (NH), 3 200 (NH), 2 990 (C-H), 1 620 (C=N), 1 170 (C=S)
3m	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	209	68	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ S	3 430 (NH), 3 200 (NH), 2 990 (C-H), 1 620 (C=N), 1 170 (C=S)
3n	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	206	66	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	3 420 (NH), 3 200 (NH), 2 990 (C-H), 1 620 (C=N), 1 170 (C=S)
4a	C ₆ H ₅	Phenyl	193	80	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₂ OS	—
4b	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	207	48	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ N ₂ OS	—
4c	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	212	65	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ OS	—
4d	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	223	72	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	—
4e	CH ₃	Phenyl	155	80	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₂ OS	—
4f	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	145	68	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ OS	—
4g	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	190	90	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ClN ₂ OS	—
4h	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	186	78	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ S	—
4i	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	201	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	—
5a	C ₆ H ₅	Phenyl	230	75	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ OS	3 200 (NH), 2 900 (C-H), 1 240 (C=S)
5b ^f	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	232	68	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₂ OS	3 200 (NH), 2 925 (C-H), 1 240 (C=S)
5c ^g	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	210	65	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ OS	3 200 (NH), 2 900 (C-H), 1 240 (C=S)
5d ^h	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	240	62	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	3 200 (NH), 2 900 (C-H), 1 240 (C=S)
5e ⁱ	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	224	69	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	3 200 (NH), 2 900 (C-H), 1 240 (C=S)
5f	C ₆ H ₅	Methyl	253	70	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₂ OS	3 200 (NH), 2 920 (C-H), 1 240 (C=S)
5g	C ₆ H ₅	Ethyl	222	72	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₂ OS	3 200 (NH), 2 920 (C-H), 1 240 (C=S)
5h	C ₆ H ₅	<i>n</i> -Propyl	218	59	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₂ OS	3 200 (NH), 2 920 (C-H), 1 170 (C=S)
5i	CH ₃	Phenyl	228	72	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ OS	3 200 (NH), 2 920 (C-H), 1 170 (C=S)
5j	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	225	75	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₂ OS	3 200 (NH), 2 920 (C-H), 1 170 (C=S)
5k ^j	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	220	73	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ ClN ₂ OS	3 200 (NH), 2 920 (C-H), 1 170 (C=S)
5l	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	227	72	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ S	3 200 (NH), 2 920 (C-H), 1 170 (C=S)
5m	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	212	76	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	3 200 (NH), 2 920 (C-H), 1 170 (C=S)

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses. ^a*m/z M*⁺ 409. ^b*m/z M*⁺ 429. ^c (DMSO-d₆) 2.3–2.5 (1H, s, NH), 5.9–6.1 (1H, s, NH), 7.1–7.2 (14H, m, 2×ArH and 1-Cl-C₆H₄), *m/z M*⁺ 429. ^d*m/z M*⁺ 425. ^e*m/z M*⁺ 439. ^f (DMSO-d₆) 2.4–2.6 (1H, s, NH), 5.7–5.9 (1H, NH), 2.2 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.5 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.1–7.9 (5H, C₆H₅), *m/z M*⁺ 305. ^g*m/z M*⁺ 409. ^h (DMSO-d₆) 6.0–6.2 (1H, s, NH), 7.0–7.8 (15H, m, 2×ArH, *p*-ClC₆H₄ and NH). ⁱ*m/z M*⁺ 429. ^j*m/z M*⁺ 425. ^k*m/z M*⁺ 439. ^l*m/z M*⁺ 305.

R³=Alkyl/aryl
Scheme 2

aqueous dimethyl formamide rearranged to 4-anilino-1,2-dihydroquinazoline-2-thione⁷. In the ir spectrum

of compound 5, the sharp peak at 2 200 cm⁻¹ (CN) was absent indicating that no ring-opened compound was formed. The ¹H nmr spectrum of 5c showed a broad singlet at δ 6.0–6.2 (1H) due to NH, a complex multiplet at δ 7.0–7.8 (15H) due to aryl protons of the two phenyl groups, 1-*p*-chlorophenyl group and one aniline-type NH proton. The structure was further confirmed from its mass spectrum. The molecular ion peak appeared at *m/z* 429 and 431. In the mass spectrum of 5c, significant elimination of *p*-ClC₆H₄NH₂⁺ could be observed whereas in that of 3c the formation of *p*-ClC₆H₄NCS⁺ was found. No such fragmentation was evident in the mass

spectrum of 5c. The characterisation data of 5a-m are given in Table 1.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The purity of the products was ascertained by tlc using silica gel (Merck, GE 254).

Mass spectra were recorded on a Hewlett-Packard 5995 spectrometer (70 eV) and ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 397 spectrophotometer. The required 2-amino-3-cyano-4,5-diphenylfuran and 2-amino-3-cyano-4,5-dimethylfuran were prepared according to the reported procedures⁸.

5,6-Diphenyl-4-imino-3-phenylfuro[2,3-d]pyrimidine-2-thione (3a): To a suspension of 2-amino-3-cyano-4,5-diphenylfuran (**1a**; 2.6 g, 0.01 mol) in dimethyl formamide (10 ml) containing powdered sodium hydroxide (0.4 g, 0.01 mol), phenyl isothiocyanate (1.35 g, 0.01 mol) was added dropwise and stirred till the pungent smell of isothiocyanate vanished (~2 h). On dilution of the mixture and acidification, the pale yellow precipitate obtained was crystallised from ethanol as shining yellow needles (2.9 g, 74%), m.p. 217° (Found: C, 72.9; H, 4.2; N, 10.5; S, 8.0. C₂₄H₁₇N₃OS requires: C, 72.9; H, 4.3; N, 10.6, S, 8.1%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 350s (NH), 3 200m (NH), 2 990s (CH), 1 620s (C=NH) and 1 240s cm⁻¹ (C=S). Other furopyrimidines (Table 1) were prepared similarly.

4-Imino-5,6-diphenyl-2-methylthio-3-phenylfuro-[2,3-d]pyrimidine(4a): To a solution of 5,6-diphenyl-4-imino-3-phenylfuro[2,3-d]pyrimidine-2-thione (0.5 g) in sodium hydroxide solution (5%; 10 ml), methyl iodide (1 g) was added and stirred for 10 min. The

resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol as pale yellow needles (0.4 g, 72%), m.p. 193°.

4-Arylamino-5,6-diphenylfuro[2,3-d]pyrimidine-2-thione (5a): A solution of 5,6-diphenyl-4-imino-3-phenylfuro[2,3-d]pyrimidine-2-thione (**2a**; 3.95 g, 0.01 mol) in aqueous dimethyl formamide (50 ml; 1:1) was refluxed for 2 h when tlc examination indicated complete disappearance of the starting material. The reaction mixture was then cooled and the resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol as pale yellow plates (3 g, 75%), m.p. 230° (Found: C, 72.0; H, 4.1; N, 10.7; S, 8.4. C₂₄H₁₇N₃OS requires: C, 72.9; H, 4.3; N, 10.6 and S, 8.1%).

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